

EFFECT OF INDIGENOUS ECTOMYCORRHIZAL FUNGI ON GROWTH OF RUBBER (*Hevea brasiliensis* Mull Arg.) IN FOREST BIOLOGICAL EDUCATION AND RESEARCH OF ANDALAS UNIVERSITY

Stia Prihatiningsih Idris (2010422028) - Department of Biology, Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences, Andalas University

The fields of study of biology that I choose in this assignment are plant physiology and microbiology. Plant physiology is the study of the function of plant parts, while microbiology is the study of microorganisms. I chose the field of plant physiology because I am interested in conducting research related to the function of plant parts, which in this assignment discusses the physiology of the rubber plant (*Hevea brasiliensis* Mull Arg.) in Forest Biology Education and Research, Andalas University. Then the relationship between the field of microbiology and the theme I chose was the effect of Indigenous ectomycorrhizal fungus on the growth of the rubber plant (*Hevea brasiliensis* Mull Arg.). The first reason I chose this theme is because there has been no previous research on this effect. Previous research on the effect of Indigenous Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi (FMA) on rubber plants (*Hevea brasiliensis* Mull Arg.). The second reason is what is the difference between rubber plants treated with Indigenous ectomycorrhizal fungi and those given Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi (AMF). The third reason is that the diversity of ectomycorrhizal fungi has been investigated in the Biological Research and Education Forest of Andalas University.

Rubber plant (*Hevea brasiliensis* Mull Arg.) is a plantation crop that plays a very important role in the national economy, among others, as a source of income for more than 10 million farmers and absorbs about 1.7 million other workers. Heru and Andoko (2008) stated that rubber plants are relatively tolerant of infertile soils, erratic rainfall and daily temperatures and have a high level of tolerance for pests and diseases. One strategy to increase the resilience of rubber seedlings transferred to the field is to provide seedlings with mycorrhizae. Provision or provision of rubber seeds with Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi (AMF) can increase and maintain growth in non-ideal soil conditions (Yuleli, 2009). Of course, in this case, Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi (AMF) are used instead of ectomycorrhizal fungi. Research on the effect of indigenous ectomycorrhizal fungi has never been done, but what has been done is the effect of Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi (AMF) on the growth of rubber plants (*Hevea brasiliensis* Mull Arg.). The ectomycorrhizal fungus is one of the most important elements of the forest ecosystem because it infects forest plants. The ectomycorrhizal fungi obtain their carbon source from the host plant. The contributions of ectomycorrhizal fungi in association with plants include increasing nutrient and water absorption, increasing drought resistance, increasing disease resistance, and as bioindicators of forest soil productivity. Ectomycorrhizal fungi are commonly found in nature, associated with various tropical trees including Dipterocarpaceae, Eucalyptus and Pinus (Smith and Read, 2008) and Gnetaceae (Wulandari 2002). The ectomycorrhizal-forming fungi belong to the Basidiomycetes group which are usually in the form of an umbrella (mushrooms) or balls (puffballs). One of the characteristics of ectomycorrhizal fungi is that it is specific for each type of host plant and certain site conditions. From one type of host plant, it is possible to have several types of ectomycorrhizal fungi that become symbionts and from one type of ectomycorrhizal fungi to symbiotically with several types of host plants (Darwo and Sugiarti, 2008). In general, ectomycorrhizal can only be symbiotic with a few plants such as pine. In this case, whether ectomycorrhizal can also be in symbiosis with rubber plants or not, which will have an impact on the rubber plants themselves.

Rubber plants (*Hevea brasiliensis* Mull Arg.) treated with Indigenous ectomycorrhizal fungi and Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi (AMF) certainly have different yields and will affect their growth. Based on the structure and the way the fungus infects the roots, mycorrhizae can be grouped into Ectomycorrhizae (infecting fungi do not enter plant root cells and only develop between the cell walls of the cortical tissue, infected roots enlarge and branch), Endomycorrhizae (infecting fungi enter the plant tissue) infected cortical and root cells do not enlarge). Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi (AMF) is a fungus that belongs to the endomycorrhizal group. The number and level of inoculated spore infection are factors that affect the growth and development of mycorrhizae and affect their relationship to plants. Differences in plant response to AMF are closely related to the level of infection. The response of AMF with plants is increasing in line with the increase in the level of AMF infection in plant roots (Farda *et al.*, 2012). The compatibility between Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi (AMF) and the host plant was also influenced by the type of AMF used. Indigenous mycorrhizae are mycorrhizae that have a high potential to form intensive infections because they can recognize their host plants quickly, so that indigenous AMF will have a better role in promoting plant growth than introduced AMF (Delvian 2006). Based on the research that has been done, it can be concluded that the appropriate dose of AMF Indigenous HPPB for the growth of rubber seedlings is 10 g/seedling. The growth of rubber seedlings and number of leaves at a dose of 10 g was faster than the other doses. The average dry weight of stems, leaves and roots was higher at a dose of 10 g compared to other doses (Akhyar Salim *et al.*, 2015). Ectomycorrhizal infection begins with the growth of spores on the plant surface. In plants with low density, and the native line is less efficient than the inoculated line, the application of ectomycorrhizae on plant roots will provide benefits for plants because it can increase plant growth (Susanto, 2002). Based on this research, it is estimated whether the ectomycorrhizae used will also affect the growth of rubber plants (*Hevea brasiliensis* Mull Arg.).

The diversity of ectomycorrhizal fungi has been studied in the Biology Research and Education Forest, Andalas University. The diversity of ectomycorrhizal fungi in HPPB consisted of 16 species (*Scleroderma sinnamariense*, *S.columnare*, *S.citrinum*, *Amanita sp1*, *Amanita sp2*, *Amanita sp3*, *Amanita sp4*, *Amanita sp5*, *Laccaria sp*, *Lactarius sp1*, *Lactarius sp2*, *Lactarius sp3*, *Russula sp1*, *Russula sp2*, *R.cyanoxhanta*, *R.delica*), which belong to 4 families (Sclerodermataceae, Amanitaceae, Tricholomataceae, and Russulaceae) (Feskaharny Alamsjah, 2016). The forest for biological education and research is located in the Andalas Limau Manis University campus area, with an area of 150 ha. In general, HPPB is classified as secondary forest, characterized by the discovery of many open areas and the discovery of many pioneer plant species. In general, lowland forest is dominated by Dipterocarpaceae, while in HPPB it is dominated by Fagaceae. Fagaceae are generally found in areas above 600 m asl, or are usually distributed in areas with higher altitudes in the tropics. This phenomenon may be related to the presence of indigenous ectomycorrhizal fungi associated with Fagaceae plants in HPPB. Biological education and research forest located at an altitude of 260 – 465 m above sea level has a unique vegetation because it is dominated by Fagaceae. According to Chairul and Yoneda (1997), the structure and species composition of the lowland tropical forests of Sumatra have different characteristics. Therefore, the diversity of ectomycorrhizae is found in the forest for education and biological research at Andalas University, so that it can be used as a location for research on the effect of ectomycorrhizae on the growth of rubber plants (*Hevea brasiliensis* Mull Arg.).

The conclusion from the above discussion is that there may be an effect of ectomycorrhizae on rubber plants (*Hevea brasiliensis* Mull Arg.). This is because ectomycorrhizae can have symbiosis with plant roots. Plants associated with ectomycorrhizae will have better growth than plants that are not

associated. The effect of endomycorrhizae such as Arbuscular Mycorrhizal Fungi (AMF) can increase the growth of rubber plants (*Hevea brasiliensis* Mull Arg.). This of course can also be evidence that ectomycorrhizae can be associated with rubber plants because they both come from mycorrhizal clones.

REFERENCES

- Alamsjah, Feskaharny. (2016). The Diversity of Ectomycorrhizal Fungi In The School of Biology Forest (SBF) of Andalas University and Their Influence On The Growth Of (*Lithocarpus urceolaris* (JACK) MERR.) Seedlings. *Disertasi*. Padang: Andalas University.
- Chairul and T. Yoneda. (1997). Phenological of Fagaceous Trees in a Lowland Tropical Rainforest, West Sumatera. *Annual Report of FBRT Project. No.3*. Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA). Andalas University.
- Darwo dan Sugiarti. (2008). Beberapa jenis Cendawan Ektomikoriza di Kawasan Hutan Sipirok, Tongkoh, dan Aek Nauli, Sumatera Utara. *Jurnal Penelitian Hutan dan Konservasi Alam*, (2): 157-173.
- Delvian. (2006). *Peranan Ekologi Dan Agronomi Cendawan Mikoriza Arbuskula*. Departemen Kehutanan. Fakultas Pertanian. Universitas Sumatera Utara.
- Farda, E. H., Syarif, A., Kasil. (2012). *Mikoriza Sebagai Pendukung Sistem Pertanian Berkelanjutan dan Berwawasan Lingkungan*. Padang: Andalas University Press.
- Heru, D.S dan Andoko, A. (2008). *Petunjuk Lengkap Budi Daya Karet*. Jakarta. Agro Media Pustaka.
- Salim, Akhyar, Zozy Aneloi Noli, dan Suwirman. (2015). Pertumbuhan Bibit Karet (*Hevea brasiliensis* Mull Arg.) Setelah Pemberian Beberapa Dosis Fungi Mikoriza Arbuskula (FMA) Indigineous Dari Hutan Pendidikan Dan Penelitian Biologi (HPPB) Universitas Andalas Padang. *Jurnal Biologi Universitas Andalas*, 4(1): 31-37.
- Smith, S.E dan D.J. Read. (2008). *Mycorrhizal Symbiosis*. 3rd Edition. London: Academic Press.
- Susanto, R. (2002). *Penerapan Pertanian Organik Masyarakat dan Pengembangannya*. Yogyakarta: Karnisius.
- Wulandari, A.S. (2002). Beberapa Gatra Biologi Ektomikoriza Scleroderma pada Melinjo. *Disertasi*. Bogor: Program Pascasarjana, Institut Pertanian Bogor.
- Yuleli. (2009). Penggunaan Beberapa Jenis Fungi Untuk Meningkatkan Tanaman Karet (*Hevea brasiliensis*) di Tanah Gambut. *Tesis Program studi biologi Pascasarjana Universitas Sumatera Utara*. Medan <http://repository.usu.ac.id/bitstream/123456789/5793/1/09E01975.pdf>. Diakses Tanggal 1 Maret 2012.